

DETERMINATION OF EFFECTIVE THERMAL AND THERMO-ELASTIC PROPERTIES OF WOVEN TEXTILE COMPOSITES USING VOXEL BASED VARIATIONAL ASYMPTOTIC UNIT CELL HOMOGENIZATION METHOD

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ABSTRACT

The present paper is concerned about the development of voxel based variational asymptotic method (VAM) homogenization technique as applied to woven composites to determine their thermal/thermo-elastic properties in two stages. In the first stage, the resin impregnated fibre bundle is homogenized to obtain its effective thermal/thermo-elastic properties, which is subsequently used in the second stage to homogenize the woven composite RUC. The properties obtained are compared with the tested properties from literature. VAM based homogenization technique was found to be computationally efficient and capable of predicting the homogenized properties of the woven composites both quantitatively and qualitatively.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composites are increasingly being used in thermally severe environments. Their application has gained momentum with the introduction of textile composites. The wide applications of textile composites in thermally challenging environments can be attributed to its integral fiber architecture and its resistance to thermal shock. Textile preforms of carbon fiber have been used to form carbon-carbon(C/C) and ceramic matrix composites(CMC), which finds use in ultra-high temperature environment. Woven textile composites are being used in cell phone covers, fire resistant clothes etc. In order to maximize the effective application of these composites, its material properties need to be quantified accurately. This has led to the development of several micromechanical models (see Ref. [1, 2, and 3]) that yield homogenized material properties.

Several analytical [4] and numerical methods [5, 6] have been developed for the determination of effective properties for composites. Numerical methods are predominantly based on FEM, see Ref. [7, 8], which has been generally used with conformal meshing of the unit cells. However, for complex material architectures this becomes very time consuming. In Ref. [6] this was overcome by adopting a voxel based technique to automate the grid generation process. Voxel based technique has also been used to predict thermo-mechanical properties in Ref. [7]; however, series of finite element analyses (FEAs) are required to find the response of the cell to normal and shear strains and uniform temperature changes. Most of the methods mentioned above have been extended to predict coupled physical properties like thermo-elastic properties. Variational asymptotic method unit cell homogenization (VAMUCH) technique was used in [9, 10, 11] to predict the effective thermo-elastic, electro-magneto-elastic and piezoelectric properties respectively. Here, following the method in [12], the periodicity was considered as a small parameter and was used in expanding the energy functional

asymptotically to obtain a variational statement for the unit cell. The minimization of this statement yielded the required governing equation and boundary conditions. The numerical implementation was done using FEM. Variational Asymptotic Method (VAM) provides an efficient analytical tool to determine the properties by homogenization of a Repeating Unit Cell (RUC) of the composite material. When compared to FEM based methods, VAM does not require loading of the RUC to determine the effective property and thus is highly efficient.

VAMUCH has been successfully used to homogenize a wide class of heterogeneous materials [13]. It has also been successfully used to determine the effective thermo-elastic as well as thermal properties for simple geometry in [14]. In the present paper, voxel based VAM was applied to woven composites from [15] and the thermal properties (thermal conductivity and specific heat) as well as thermo-elastic properties (coefficient of thermal expansion) were determined. First, the resin impregnated fibre bundle was homogenized to obtain its effective thermal/thermo-elastic properties, which was subsequently used to homogenize the woven composite RUC. The results are compared with the data reported in [15].

2 VAM BASED UNIT CELL HOMOGENIZATION OF PERIODICALLY HETEROGENEOUS MATERIALS

In this section a brief description of the VAMUCH model based on Ref. [17] is given. The periodicity of the heterogeneous material is considered as a small parameter and a variational statement of the unit cell is formulated through an asymptotic expansion of the energy functional given in Eq. 1 for all the mosaics.

$$\Pi = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} K_{ij} \phi_{,i} \phi_{,j} d\Omega \quad (1)$$

here, K_{ij} are components of the second order conductivity tensor and $\phi_{,i}$ is the thermal gradient field .

The variational statement of the energy functional was solved using variational asymptotic method (VAM) to determine the relation between local and global fields. Further, due to the variational structure of the problem the periodic boundary conditions were naturally derived during the energy minimization process. Following the steps described in Ref. [17], the governing equations for the unit cell were derived. Subsequently, the energy functional described below was minimized,

$$\Pi_{\Omega} = \frac{1}{2\Omega} \int_{\Omega} K_{ij} (\Psi_{,i} + \zeta_{,i})(\Psi_{,j} + \zeta_{,j}) d\Omega \quad (2)$$

where, $\Psi_{,i}$ is the global thermal gradient and $\zeta_{,i}$ is the gradient of fluctuating function.

The minimization of Eq. 2 was carried out under the following constraints,

$$\zeta^{+i} = \zeta^{-i} \quad \text{for } i = 1, 2, 3 \quad (3)$$

This was done by making the nodes on +ve face of unit cell the slave of -ve face nodes.

Introducing the following matrix notation

$$\phi = [\Psi_{,1}, \Psi_{,2}, \Psi_{,3}]^T \quad (4)$$

$$\Psi_{,1} = \begin{Bmatrix} \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial y1} \\ \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial y2} \\ \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial y3} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \frac{\partial}{\partial y1} \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial y2} \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial y3} \end{Bmatrix} \zeta = \Gamma_h \zeta \quad (5)$$

where, Γ_h is a gradient operator matrix. On discretizing the fluctuating function using the finite elements as,

$$\zeta = N\xi \quad (6)$$

where N , is the shape function matrix and ξ is a vector of nodal values of fluctuating function; we can write the energy functional as,

$$\Pi_{\Omega} = \frac{1}{2\Omega} (\xi^T F \xi + 2\xi^T K_{h\phi} \xi + \phi^T K_{\phi\phi} \phi) \quad (7)$$

In which,

$$F = \int_{\Omega} (\Gamma_h N)^T K (\Gamma_h N) d\Omega \quad , \quad K_{h\phi} = \int_{\Omega} (\Gamma_h N)^T K d\Omega \quad \text{and} \quad K_{\phi\phi} = \int_{\Omega} K d\Omega \quad (8)$$

Here, K is 3x3 conductivity matrix. By minimizing π_{Ω} we obtain the following equation,

$$F\xi = -K_{h\phi}\phi \quad (9)$$

It can be ascertained that ξ is linearly proportional to ϕ , hence

$$\xi = \xi_0 \phi \quad (10)$$

By using the above inference we can calculate the integral energy density of the unit cell as

$$\Pi_{\Omega} = \frac{1}{2\Omega} \phi^T (\xi_0^T K_{h\phi} + K_{\phi\phi}) \phi \equiv \frac{1}{2} \phi^T K^* \phi \quad (11)$$

K^* is the effective thermal conductivity matrix and ϕ is the global temperature gradient. In a similar procedure, expression for determination of effective elastic constitutive matrix as well as effective coefficient of thermal expansion has been derived in [13].

3 PROBLEM DEFINITION

As a verification problem, the experimentally tested woven composite from Ref. [15] is considered in this work.

3.1 DEFINITION OF RUC FOR WOVEN COMPOSITE

The RUC of the woven composite is shown in Fig. 1. The parametric variation was carried out and the effective properties for different fiber volume fraction of the RUC were determined.

Fig. 1 Geometric Parameter defining Woven Composite RUC

The material property of E-glass fiber and epoxy resin from Ref. [15] is reported in Table 1.

Property	E-glass(fiber)	Epoxy(matrix)
E(GPa)	72.4	3.45
ν	0.22	0.37
α ($\mu\epsilon/^\circ\text{C}$)	5.4	69.0
k (W/m/K)	1.03	0.19

Table 1. E-glass fiber and epoxy properties [15]

3.2 VOXELIZATION

The process of voxelization takes the curve definition for a yarn and a voxel grid of the RUC as input. The subvoxels inside each voxels are used to calculate the volume fraction and average orientation of the fiber inside each voxel. This information is then used to calculate the material matrix using the average orientation and then it is weighted using the volume fraction. Each voxel is a 8 noded hexahedral element that takes these average properties to calculate the stiffness matrix for each element. The process of voxelization is depicted diagrammatically in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Voxelization of Woven Composite RUC

4. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Using the fiber and matrix property from Table-1, we obtained the effective properties of the impregnated fiber yarn using VAM as a first stage homogenization. The effective properties for the fiber yarn with a $V_f = 0.65$ is presented in Table-2.

E_L (GPa)	E_T (GPa)	ν_{LT}	α_L ($\mu\epsilon/^\circ\text{C}$)	α_T ($\mu\epsilon/^\circ\text{C}$)	k_L (W/m/K)	k_T (W/m/K)
48.13	19.11	0.262	7.40	29.60	0.734	0.516

Table 2. Effective thermo-mechanical properties of E-glass/epoxy yarn($V_f = 0.65$)

The next stage of homogenization was done on the woven composite RUC (ref. Fig 3), where the effective properties from Table-2 were used for the fiber yarn and the matrix properties were used from Table-1.

Fig. 3 Voxel Model of Woven Composite RUC

The effective conductivity in the plane and thickness direction was computed for different volume fractions, and is tabulated in Table-3.

Vf	Conductivity(W/m/K)							
	Analytical[15]		FEA[15]		Exp[15]		Voxel based VAM	
	In-plane	thickness	In-plane	thickness	In-plane	thickness	In-plane	thickness
0.22	0.319	0.246	0.319	0.248			0.327	0.260
0.26	0.338	0.258	0.338	0.260			0.346	0.272
0.28	0.358	0.271	0.359	0.273	0.35	0.279	0.361	0.281
0.30	0.369	0.279	0.369	0.281			0.374	0.289
0.33	0.389	0.297	0.390	0.297			0.388	0.299
0.36	0.399	0.309	0.399	0.309			0.407	0.311

Table 3: Comparison of Effective thermal conductivity

Predictions from the current model show good agreement with those reported in Ref. [15]. When the volume fraction of the woven composite is increased by 64%, the in-plane conductivity increases by 24%, whereas this increases only by 19% along the thickness direction. The same composite was analyzed for effective thermo-mechanical properties and the effective thermo-mechanical properties for a volume fraction of 0.35 and the predictions are tabulated in Table-4.

	Numerical[15]	Experimental[15]	VAM
E_x, E_y (GPa)	19.7	18.8	18.2
ν_{xy}	.14	.14	0.16
α_x, α_y ($\mu\epsilon/^\circ\text{C}$)	17.6	15.0	20.0
α_z ($\mu\epsilon/^\circ\text{C}$)	54.2	58.1	52.5

Table 4. Effective thermo-mechanical properties of E-glass/epoxy woven composite(Vf=0.35)

9 CONCLUSIONS

A voxel based variational asymptotic method unit cell homogenization procedure was developed. The framework is capable of handling complex material architectures by avoiding the manual mesh

generation process. Voxel based method is automatic and is capable of accurately describing the local heterogeneity in the material without the need for fine grids; thus improving the computational efficiency of the model. The framework was used to determine the effective thermo-elastic and thermal properties of 3D woven composites. Model predictions matched well with the experimental results and confirmed the veracity of the framework.

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